

POPULATION COUNT AND MANAGEMENT OF AFGHAN PIKA (*OCHOTONA RUFESCENS*) IN APPLE ORCHARDS OF ZIARAT CITY (DISTRICT ZIARAT), BALOCHISTAN

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Abstract

The Afghan pika is a destructive vertebrate pest that debarks the apple trees in Ziarat valley, Balochistan. It attacks trunks and other main limbs, especially of young apple trees in winter. While in summer, it eats or damages peas, potatoes, wheat, and corn. The damage caused by this pest according to literature reduces 30% of apple production annually resulting in great loss to growers. The apple varieties like Kaja, Red Delicious and Golden Delicious are known to be the cash crop of district Ziarat and the main source of income. To get rid of pika destruction and to promote apple production in the area, the present study was carried out in 2021 and 2022. The population count, damages assessment, and control of this pest were done in two apples (plots) orchards located at Killi Zaar Gaat (30°.36'N, 67°.69'E) and Killi Murdar Kaas (30.35'N, 67.66'E). Both the apple plots were of equal size with a 150 square meter area. The results showed in total 154 pikas trapped by steel rat snap trap and chemical control methods using pesticide (Zinc phosphide) in the following composition: adult male 45/102 (44.11%), adult female 36/102 (35.29%) and juvenile pikas 21/102 (20.58%). The difference indicated a high adult population compared to the juvenile. The pesticide killed 52 pikas, including 23 (45.09%) adult males, 15 (29.41%) adult females, and 13 (25.49%) juvenile were recorded. The damage percentage to apple trees was 22% (70/250 trees) during the months of January and February 2022. Out of the 70 trees, 15

(21.42%) were damaged completely, while 55 (78.57%) were found partially damaged. From the result of this study, it is concluded that the high fertility of pika evidently empowers them to respond quickly to favorable weather conditions by a large increase in compactness and by inhabiting previously empty areas. This characteristic enhances its potential as a pest species to survive in large numbers. Therefore, proper monitoring of pest population using snap traps at the time of peak emergence and pesticides with recommended usage is suggested.

KEYWORDS: Afghan Pika, apple damages, control strategies, Ziarat Balochistan.

INTRODUCTION

Pika or afghan Pika (Mammalia: Lagomorpha), also known as collared pika or reddish pika founds almost in cold regions with 6000 to 8000 feet elevation from the sea (Shafi et al., 1992). They make burrows in rocky mountain steppe forests, which protect them from predators (Travina et al., 2000). Afghan pika, (*Ochotona rufescens* Gray, 1842) has four sub species viz *Ochotona rufescens regina* from Turkmenistan and from Khorud range in Iran, *Ochotona rufescens vultuma* from Balochistan, *Ochotona rufescens vizier* and *Ochotona rufescens shukurovi* from Greater Balkhans range in Turkmenistan (Khalilipour et al., 2014). *O. rufescens* is found in Afghanistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Iran, and Pakistan. The pika of these regions inhabits narrow valleys of 30 to 40% grassy-covered juniper mountains. As a vertebrate pest, it is herbivorous and takes food from feeding on a variety of grasses, leaves, ephedra, thistle, and xeric plant (Smith et al., 1990), but their primary diet is folivore. Foraging manners differ pika from other mammals in that they store hay piles in their burrows twice a year during spring and fall.

The body of the afghan pika is almost rounded and fully covered with a soft and reddish-brown furry coat dependent on the seasons. Body size range from 15 cm to 23 cm with an average weight of 125 to 400 g. The tail is absent; the forelegs are slightly shorter than the hind legs, sexes are separate and sexual dimorphism is absent (Sahnehs et al., 2014). The first generation can give birth in mid-summer, and the population rises to 70 individuals per hectare. Still, the number variation is highly dependent on the weather changes (Shafi et al., 1992). Pika breeds for a long period annually, from early March to the end of September and produces 5 to 7 offspring per year (Smith et al., 2019). One of the basic causes of its limited population size is farmers' behavior because they treat it as a pest. Pika grows and reproduces gently in agriculture rather than in nonagricultural fields (Smith, Formozov, Hoffmann, Changlin, & Erbajeva, 1990).

Afghan pika is a diurnal animal and communicates through a whistling sound due to the less developed larynx. Its peak activity has been observed early in the morning and before sunset. To avoid warm weather, it mostly takes shelter and remains hidden in burrows (Ivins & Smith, 1983). Some snake species, especially the Levantine viper (Squamata: Viperidae), are significantly predated afghan pika, and this viper is abundantly found in Southwestern Turkmenia (Central Asian Republic). Therefore, the animal remains alert to handle any threat (Danov, 1985). Pika can mark their territory by chemical cues, e.g., scent marks, like other mammals, and perception behavior is very well in communication (Smith & Ivins, 1984).

Being an agricultural pest, it damages apple trees, garden vegetables (peas, potatoes), wheat, and corn. According to Fulk & Khokhar (1980), 20 percent of 2497 apple trees were damaged by pika in the spring of 1976 in the adjacent area of District Ziarat. In the winter season, snow covers native grasses resulting in food scarcity, which diverts the pika to gnaw apple tree trunks and branches. As a result, debarking leads either to weaken or wilt the tree. Literature reports wilting of 0.15% to 5.1% and harming 1.5% to 47.1% of apple trees (*U.S. Department of Agriculture Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service Wildlife Services U.S. Government Publication, 1987*).

The aim of this research article is to enumerate the pika population, employ control strategies, and estimate the rate of damage to apple trees in the study area. According to the reported literature and best of our knowledge, no detailed works on pika population density, control measures, and damages to apple trees have been done in Ziarat city, Balochistan, except for the works previously done on pika control problem (Khan and Symethe, 1980) and an observational study on the natural history of pika (Fulk and Khokhar, 1980). Therefore, the results of this study will be helpful for future research and will also be useful for farmers of the area to understand the decrease in population rise and control the damages caused by the pika in this region of the province.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study sites

The present study was carried out during the span from April 2021 to March 2022 in apple orchards lies in the north of Ziarat city, district Ziarat (30°20'N, 67°45'E) (Fig.1). The orchards were located in two localities namely Killi Murder Kass and Killi Zaar Gaat were selected (Figure 2 a & b). The area is an upland of Balochistan province (Pakistan) with an altitude of 8200 feet (2499.36 meters), average annual temperature (Minimum 18.94°C and

maximum 31.17°C July and January), and precipitation (13.83mm) (Fareed, Memon, Bhatti, & Keerio, 2021).

Figure 1: (a) Map of Pakistan showing Balochistan & district Ziarat. (b) Map of Ziarat. Red shows the study area.

Figure 2: Study areas. (a) Plot-1 (Murder Kass site), (b) Plot-2 (Zaar Gaat site) near

Ziarat city.*Pika trapping and population count****Installation of traps***

Twenty steel rat snap traps were set at a 5-meter distance in a row near a stony wall boundary inside two apple plots of equal sizes (150 m × 150 m). Traps were baited with apple slices and pea pods. The population of trapped pikas was counted for record. The shrubs, bags, and bottles were tied around the tree trunks depending upon the length of the trunks.

Pesticide usage

Zinc phosphide (an organophosphate pesticide) was used to kill the pest for count and control purposes in the two field plots. The number of killed pikas was counted for record. The population count of adult male, female, and juvenile pikas was taken every month during the morning and evening in two apples (plots) orchards distanced 4 kilometers from each other. Adult male, female, and juveniles pikas were captured upon emergence using steel rat snap trap methods (baited with pea pods and apple slices) (Khan & Smythe, 1980) of equal sizes (150 m × 150 m) figure 3 (a & b).

Figure 3: Sample collection. (a) Arrow show steel rat snap trap, (b) Arrow show trapped pika.

Damage ratio

Apple trees were inspected daily during the months of January and February 2022. The number of damaged trees (trunks and branches) was recorded, and their mean (average) was calculated. The photographs of steel rat snap traps, trapped/killed specimens, healthy and injured apple trees, and localities were taken with the help of a digital camera (Nikon DCL 511, Japan).

Statistical analysis

For data analysis, Microsoft Excel (2016) was employed. The data were processed and analyzed, and the construction of clustered bar charts was performed.

RESULTS

In the present study, in total, 152 *Ochotona rufescens* (Pika or Afghan pika) were recorded as a destructive pest in the two localities of apple orchards in the upland's valley of Ziarat, Balochistan. Of the total 152, 102 pikas were captured by the conventional trap method, and 50 individuals were killed by pesticides (Zinc phosphide, Zn_3P_2), as shown in table 1, 2 & figure 4, and 5, respectively.

Population count

Of the total 102 trapped pikas, 45 were adult males, 36 were adult females, and 21 were juvenile. The average trapped pikas per month were calculated as 9.27. While of the total 52 killed pikas, 23 were adult males, 15 were adult females, and 13 were juveniles. Month-wise, the highest number of pests captured was 12, counted in October 2021, and the lowest number was 7 in December 2021 and January 2022, respectively (Table 1). The highest number of pests killed by pesticides was seven, noted in August 2021, and the lowest number was two, counted in December 2021 (Table 2). This difference may be ascribed to the grazing activities of the pest over the mentioned months. In the month of August 2021, the study area receives a high rate of rain (12.5 mm), resulting in high vegetation growth and temperate weather. In the month of December 2021, the frost weather resulted in diminished growth of vegetation, grazing, and hay pile activities. A significant difference was observed between the number of trapped and killed pests due to the observer's inability to approach the killed pikas in scattered deep barrows.

Table 1. A number of pikas were captured by a snap trap in apple plot I at Zaar Gaat Ziarat.

Months	Adult Male	Adult Female	Juvenile	Total
April 2021	4	3	2	9
May 2021	4	3	3	10
June 2021	5	2	2	9
July 2021	5	3	1	9
August 2021	6	2	2	10

September 2021	3	5	1	9
October 2021	4	6	3	12
November 2021	3	5	2	10
December 2021	4	3	0	7
January 2022	3	1	3	7
February 2022	4	3	2	9
Total	45	36	21	102

Table 2. A number of pikas were killed by pesticides in apple Plot 2 at Murdar Kaas, Ziarat.

Months	Adult Male	Adult Female	Juvenile	Total
April 2021	2	3	1	6
May 2021	1	1	2	4
June 2021	2	3	0	5
July 2021	1	2	2	5
August 2021	4	2	1	7
September 2021	3	0	1	4
October 2021	3	1	1	5
November 2021	2	0	2	4
December 2021	0	1	1	2
January 2022	2	2	0	4
February 2022	3	0	2	5
Total	23	15	13	51

Figure 4: Captured pikas population count using Steel rat snap trap in a plot I at Zaar Gaat site.

Figure 5: Population counts of pikas killed by chemicals (pesticide) in Plot 2 at murder Kass site.

Apple trees damage rate assessment

In total, 250 trees in two field plots were selected for study, of which the pest debarked 28% (70/250) trees (Table 3). Table 3 also indicates 79% (55/70 trees) and 21% (15/70 trees) as partial and complete damage to the selected apple trees, respectively. These results revealed that apple trees were found to be more damaged by the pest in the winter seasons (January and February) of 2022 compared to the winter (December) seasons of 2021, in which no damage to trees' trunks and branches was found/ Highest percent damage of tree trunks and branches were (22) observed in January and February 2022 because of vegetation scarcity or snow-covered surface grasses, hence the pest feed upon the bark of the trunk and other branches during the winter seasons. The whole garden would die out within the next few years if this risk were left unnoticed.

Table 3. A total number of healthy and damaged trees was observed during the present study.

Duration (month/year)	Number of a healthy tree	No. of a tree damaged	
		Partial damage	Complete damage
January 2022	150	25	5
February 2022	150	30	10

Control strategies

Different methods were applied as control measures during this study, like trapping, food baited with pesticide, ostico painting, trunk covered method, gun shooting, and catapult (Figs. 7a, b, c, d, e & f). Pesticide (Zinc phosphide) was baited with an apple slice and pea pod for killing and controlling the pikas in field plots (Table 2 & Fig. 7 a). The chemical compound, after intake by the pika, is converted into phosphine (a harmful gas) in the stomach, resulting in the pikas' murder. This organo-phosphate compound has been used as a rodenticide in the United States since 1947. Similarly, a repellent paint (Ostico) acted as a marking or warning sign for pests coated on the tree trunks and branches to prevent the pest attack positively, as shown in figure 7b. Wrapping of native herbs (*Artemisia scoparia*), blank gunny bags, plastic bottles around trees trunks and branches, and usage of short guns and catapult results in some degree of control of the pest from debarking the trees (Figs. 7c & d). However, no significant differences were observed between these methods.

Figure 6: Apple trees. (a) Healthy (b) Partially debarked (c) Completely debarked and (d) Wilted young tree.

Figure 7: Control strategies. (a) Pesticide (Zinc phosphide) (b) Ostico (c) Wrapping apple tree trunks with native twigs (d) Covering of apple tree trunks with plastic bottles (e) Catapult (f) Rat snap traps, arrow showed trapped pika.

DISCUSSION

In the light of results obtained in the present study regarding the population count using chemical and conventional methods, 102 afghan pikas were captured by trapping technique viz 81 adults (45 male, 36 female) and 21 juveniles. Similarly, 52 pikas, with 38 adults (23 male, 15 female) and 13 juveniles, were killed by chemical approach and counted. Month wise highest number of pikas was 12, recorded in October 2021. The lowest number was seven counted in December 2021 and January 2022, respectively (Fig.4). The highest and the lowest number of pikas killed by pesticide was 7 and 2 recorded in August 2021 and December 2021, respectively (Fig.5). This difference may be ascribed to the grazing activities of the pest over the mentioned months. In August 2021, the study area was observed with high vegetation growth and temperate weather because of the high rain rate (30mm). In December 2021, the severe cold weather reduced vegetation growth, grazing, and hay pile activities. A significant mean difference of 51 was observed between the number of trapped. It killed pikas due to the inability of the observer to approach the killed pikas in scattered, deep barrows.

In Ziarat during the breeding seasons (almost from mid of March to the end of September), the afghan pika, *Ochotona rufescens* (Gray,1842), gives birth to five juveniles per each female per year when compared with two juveniles for pika species *Ochotona princep* and *Ochotona hyper-borea* (Fulk & Khokhar, 1980). Moreover, the higher fecundity rate of *O. rufescens* enables it to achieve pest status by an increase in population density and thus infesting formerly empty areas. During winter, damage to apple trees has been reported to be higher (Khan & Smythe 1980, Shafi et al. 1989). It is indicated that once the natural flora is deficient in the winter season, the pikas debark the apple tree trunks or branches, resulting in the assassination of the tree and reducing fruit production. While in summer, it severely damages potatoes, wheat, and corn. It is assessed that pikas cause hundreds of thousands of dollars (U.S.) in annual apple production losses in the valley of Ziarat. Apple production in Balochistan accounts for about (52%) percent of the total provincial income through food production ((Fareed, Memon, Bhatti, & Keerio, 2021). During the two years study (2021-2022), the winter of 2022 was noted to be riskier for apple trees, and then its decline process was in progress.

During the two-year study, the damages to apple trees were evaluated by inspecting each tree trunk and branch. Destruction of trees by pika was observed because of two reasons. Firstly, In the absence of vegetation (Food), pika usually gnaws the tree bark and eats it during winter. Secondly, gnawing is related to making the upper sharp front teeth

blunt because these endlessly grow (Smith & Weston, 1990). The Zinc phosphide (rodenticide) killed more pika than non-toxic paint (Ostico). The paint acted as a repellent in marking and warning signs for pests, and it also helped prevent harmful insects from crawling on the trunks of apple trees. The snap traps were more effective than gunny bags and plastic bottles used to control this pest (Figs 7d & f).

Local shrubs (*Artemisia scoparia*) showed some degree of pikas control. The above-mentioned control strategy indicated a steady decline in the rate of damage to apple trees in the two localities (Killi Zaar Gaat and Killi Murdar Kaas) of the study areas. In the present study, 70 of 250 trees (22%) were infested by the pest. These results are summarized in Table 3. Figures 6 a, b, c & d showed injury level comparison among healthy with partially and completely damaged trunks and branches, respectively. According to our observations and local apple farmers' experiences, it was observed that partially damaged trees might grow and survive during the coming years, while the fully damaged trees are likely to wilt, as shown in Figure 5d. These results are partially in line with Khokhar and Fulk (1980), who recorded that pika damaged 20 percent of 2497 apple trees in the spring seasons in the adjacent area of district Ziarat. They also reported that in the winter season, snow covers the indigenous grasses resulting in food scarcity, which diverts the pika to debark the tree trunks and branches. As a result, debarking leads either to weaken or wilt the tree. Robert (1974) reported 89.9% damage to apple trees due to pikas debarking the trunks and branches in the valley of Ziarat compared to our results was 22%. Based on four years' data (1976-1979), Khan and Smythe (1980) observed pika problems faced by the apple trees in Ziarat and reported an overall percent (7.03) damage which represented 25.96 % partial and 2.065 % complete tree damages.

Unfortunately, the farmers of apple orchards in Ziarat valley are mostly illiterate and cannot manage the pikas properly either by pesticides or other ways. To avoid damage caused by pikas, the farmers exercise some traditional protective measures, which are effective but very trying in some cases. They generally shoot the pikas with a shotgun and catapult in the spring and summer seasons and do not monitor the optimal time of pest emergence, peak activity, and damage.

According to the current study's findings, afghan pika chooses stony and forest-covered mountains and narrow valleys for their residence to avoid any danger the survival posed by the predators such as eagle (Golden eagle: Accipitridae) and wild cat (*Felis silvestris*) that might reduce the pika population. Pikas are rarely found in plain areas of Ziarat, and no damage to orchards was observed compared to the mountainous study areas.

In the past, their population was high, adversely affecting apple trees, according to some agriculturalists and farmers of different regions of Ziarat interviewed during the present study. The significant factor for agro-ecosystem survival in the Ziarat region is to mark pika control in an orchard area rather than to eliminate from adjacent areas or wide abolition of this species.

CONCLUSION

Afghan pika, one of the most threatening vertebrate pests, debarks apple tree trunks and other main branches mostly in winter when snowfall covers the native vegetation and the food of pikas becomes scarce. In the present study, trees near to stony walls of field plots were found to be highly damaged by the pest compared to the trees planted on the four inner sides of the plots. Both the apple plots were surrounded by stony boundary walls, but the spaces among stone rows that were not sealed properly provided shelter for pikas to reside compared to adjacent apple plots surrounded by a woody fenced boundary wall. The fenced boundary walls do not provide likely habitat and proper protection for pikas from predators. The infested and wilted trees planted near the boundary walls need to be replaced by new trees, which require 6 to 7 years to reach commercially bearing size. The orchard layout level in relation to tree damage is very important from a future research point of view on pika. Secondly, it is important to eliminate the breeding sites of pikas in and near the apple orchards. Lastly, conventional/ traditional methods, which are cheap and non-laborious should be applied at the time of maximum pest emergence. If the said techniques are too slow or ineffective, then agriculture pesticides (Rodenticides) plus non-toxic paint (Ostico) may be used to lower the damage level by effectively controlling the pest population.

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